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SOLUTION OF THE SPATIAL PROBLEM OF ELASTICITY THEORY FOR A HALF-SPACE SHELL

Abstract.

The article is devoted to the development of a method for solving the spatial problem of elasticity theory for a semi-infinite layer bounded by two horizontal and one vertical surfaces. Such problems are fundamental in the mechanics of deformable solids and are important for the analysis of engineering structures. The proposed approach is based on the generalized Fourier method. A key feature of the work is the application of the principle of load asymmetry to take into account the influence of the free vertical boundary. This allows the initial boundary problem for a semi-infinite layer to be reduced to a problem for an infinite layer, which greatly simplifies the mathematical apparatus. The numerical implementation of the solution of the obtained system of equations is carried out using the reduction method, which ensures high, predetermined accuracy of the final results. The proposed method allows obtaining a highly accurate calculation of the stress-strain state of a semi-infinite layer. The validation of the results is confirmed by comparison with known solutions and verification of the boundary conditions.

Keywords: elasticity theory, semi-infinite shell, generalized Fourier method, boundary value problem, stress-strain state, Lamé equations, reduction method.

Introduction. Ensuring the strength, reliability, and durability of structures is a priority in the aerospace industry and modern mechanical engineering. The desire to reduce weight and improve performance has led to the widespread use of modern materials, in particular polymer composites. However, structural elements such as wing panels, fuselage elements, hull parts, and shells often have complex geometries that include holes, cutouts, and joints, which are stress concentrators and potential sources of failure. Accurate calculation of the stress-strain state in such areas is critical for predicting the behavior of the structure under static and dynamic loads.

The study of stress-strain states, especially in composite materials, has been the subject of numerous scientific works. Modeling progressive damage in composites with notches, as shown in [1], allows predicting material failure. Understanding the relationships between the strength limits of polymer composites under different types of static loads (bending, compression, tension) is critical for design. Complications arise when analyzing multilayer composites subjected to impact loads [2, 3] and when calculating aircraft structures such as cockpit canopies. Particular attention is paid to stress concentrations around holes, as this is one of the main causes of failure [4]. Methods for minimizing thermal stresses in perforated composite plates are being investigated, and analytical solutions are being developed to determine stresses around holes in functionally graded materials.

There are two main approaches to solving such complex problems in elasticity theory: numerical and analytical. Numerical methods, among which the finite element method, described in detail in [5], plays a leading role, allow modeling objects of complex geometry

and taking into account the nonlinear behavior of materials. Modern software packages, such as ANSYS Discovery [6], provide powerful tools for performing static structural analysis. However, numerical methods require significant computational resources, and the accuracy of the result depends on the quality of the constructed mesh. Comparative analysis of analytical and numerical methods, conducted in [7], shows that each approach has its advantages and disadvantages, and combining them often gives the best results.

Analytical methods, although applicable to a narrower class of problems, allow us to obtain a solution in general form, which provides a deeper understanding of physical processes. The fundamental basis for analytical solutions to dynamic problems is laid down in classical works on the theory of diffraction and the propagation of harmonic oscillations and waves in elastic bodies [8–11]. One of the most powerful analytical tools for solving spatial problems in elasticity theory is the generalized Fourier method. The theoretical foundations of this method and its application to a wide range of problems are described in detail in the monograph by A. G. Nikolaev and V. S. Protsenko [12].

The application of the generalized Fourier method proved to be extremely effective for solving problems for bodies with cylindrical cavities and inclusions. This method was successfully used for mathematical modeling of the dynamics of an elastic half-space with a cylindrical cavity [13, 14], for studying the wave field of a layer with a cylindrical cavity [15], and for solving mixed problems for a half-space with a cylindrical cavity and several cavities with contact conditions [16–18].

In recent works, this method has been extended to even more complex problems. In particular, it has been applied to analyze the NDS of an infinite layer with a

cylindrical cavity under periodic loading [19], as well as to analyze a fibrous composite layer and the problem of rotating a layer with a cylindrical tube around a rigid cylinder [20].

However, despite significant progress in solving problems for infinite layers and half-spaces, problems for semi-infinite bodies, i.e., bodies bounded not only by horizontal but also by vertical surfaces, remain difficult to analyze. Classical approaches often do not allow the influence of lateral boundaries to be taken into account.

The aim of this work is to develop a concept for solving the elasticity theory problem for a semi-infinite layer bounded by two horizontal surfaces and one vertical surface. To achieve this goal, we propose an approach based on the generalized Fourier method combined with the principle of load asymmetry, which allows us to satisfy the boundary conditions on the vertical free surface and reduce the problem to one already studied for an infinite layer.

Problem statement. Consider an infinite elastic sphere located in the Cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z) . This sphere is bounded by two parallel planes: the upper boundary located at a distance $y = h$ and the lower boundary located at $y = -\tilde{h}$.

The main goal of this problem is to determine the displacement field $u(x,y,z)$ and the associated stress field $\sigma(x,y,z)$ inside this sphere. This is achieved by solving the Lamé equations, which are the fundamental equations of elasticity theory. They describe the equilibrium of an elastic body and have the form:

$$(\lambda + \mu)\nabla(\nabla \cdot u) + \mu\nabla^2 u + F = 0$$

$$\vec{U}_0 = \sum_{k=1}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (H_k(\lambda, \mu) \cdot \vec{u}_k^{(+)}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu) + \tilde{H}_k(\lambda, \mu) \cdot \vec{u}_k^{(-)}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu)) d\mu d\lambda \quad (3)$$

where $H_k(\lambda, \mu)$ and $\tilde{H}_k(\lambda, \mu)$ are unknown functions that must be found from the boundary conditions $\vec{u}_k^{(+)}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu)$ and $\vec{u}_k^{(-)}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu)$ are the basis solutions, Lamé equations, chosen in the form [12]:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{u}_k^{\pm}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu) &= N_k^{(d)} e^{i(\lambda z + \mu x) \pm \gamma y}; \quad (4) \\ N_1^{(d)} &= \frac{1}{\lambda} \nabla; N_2^{(d)} = \frac{4}{\lambda} (\nu - 1) \vec{e}_2^{(1)} + \frac{1}{\lambda} \nabla(y \cdot) \\ &; N_3^{(d)} = \frac{i}{\lambda} \text{rot}(\vec{e}_3^{(1)} \cdot); \\ \gamma &= \sqrt{\lambda^2 + \mu^2}; -\infty < \lambda, \mu < \infty. \end{aligned}$$

$$\vec{F}_h^0(x, z) = (\tau_{yx}^{(h)}(x, z) - \tau_{yx}^{(h)}(x, |z|)) \vec{e}_x + (\sigma_y^{(h)} \vec{e}_y(x, z) - \sigma_y^{(h)} \vec{e}_y(x, |z|)) + (\tau_{yz}^{(h)} \vec{e}_z(x, z) - \tau_{yz}^{(h)} \vec{e}_z(x, |z|)), \quad (5)$$

$$\vec{F}_{\tilde{h}}^0(x, z) = (\tau_{yx}^{(\tilde{h})} \vec{e}_x(x, z) - \tau_{yx}^{(\tilde{h})} \vec{e}_x(x, |z|)) + (\sigma_y^{(\tilde{h})} \vec{e}_y(x, z) - \sigma_y^{(\tilde{h})} \vec{e}_y(x, |z|)) + (\tau_{yz}^{(\tilde{h})} \vec{e}_z(x, z) - \tau_{yz}^{(\tilde{h})} \vec{e}_z(x, |z|)), \quad (6)$$

To find the unknown equations (3), we substitute the boundary conditions (5) and (6) into the left side of (3), after first expressing them in terms of a double Fourier integral. This gives us six equations when the boundary conditions are satisfied on the flat surfaces of the layer. By removing the integrals from the right and left sides of this equation, we obtain a system of linear algebraic equations of the second kind.

where u is the displacement vector; λ and μ are Lamé constants that characterize the elastic properties of the material; F is the vector of volume forces (e.g., gravitational forces).

The solution to this equation must satisfy the boundary conditions specified on the surfaces of the layer. In this problem, the stress values at the boundaries of the layer ($y = \pm h$) are known. These are the so-called Neumann conditions, which mean that a known external load acts on the surface. This allows us to determine a specific solution from the general family of possible solutions to the equations.

The stresses at the boundaries can be written as $F\vec{U}(x, z)|_{y=h} = \vec{F}_h^0(x, z)$, $F\vec{U}(x, z)|_{y=-\tilde{h}} = \vec{F}_{\tilde{h}}^0(x, z)$, where

$$\vec{F}_h^0(x, z) = \tau_{yx}^{(h)} \vec{e}_x + \sigma_y^{(h)} \vec{e}_y + \tau_{yz}^{(h)} \vec{e}_z, \quad (1)$$

$$\vec{F}_{\tilde{h}}^0(x, z) = \tau_{yx}^{(\tilde{h})} \vec{e}_x + \sigma_y^{(\tilde{h})} \vec{e}_y + \tau_{yz}^{(\tilde{h})} \vec{e}_z. \quad (2)$$

Thus, the complete formulation of the problem boils down to finding a displacement vector $u(x,y,z)$ that:

1. Satisfies Lamé's equation inside the layer.
2. Corresponds to the specified stresses at its upper and lower boundaries.

It is necessary to take into account the vertical boundary $z \leq 0$, with given zero stresses on the surface $z = 0$.

Research Methodology. We will present the solution to the problem in the form [15] for an infinite layer. In this equation, we will reduce the term corresponding to the cylindrical cavity, resulting in:

To account for the additional vertical boundary, we introduce an additional vertical symmetry boundary—the plane $z = 0$. This technique allows us to consider only half of the layer, which greatly simplifies the mathematical calculations, since we are moving from an infinite to a semi-infinite layer (at $z \leq 0$), while the load at $z > 0$ will be taken with the opposite sign.

Thus, the specified load is in the negative zone (at $z \leq 0$). To take into account the vertical boundary in an infinite layer (to obtain a semi-infinite layer), it is necessary to replace boundary conditions (1) and (2), taking into account the asymmetric load in the positive coordinate zone of the z -axis:

Having obtained a system of equations, we expressed them as $H_k(\lambda, \mu)$ and $\tilde{H}_k(\lambda, \mu)$. As a result, all unknowns of the problem were found.

Numerical studies of the stress state. Numerical studies were carried out for a homogeneous isotropic layer of aluminum alloy D16T (Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$, modulus of elasticity $E = 7.1 \cdot 10^4$ MPa).

Geometric parameters of the model: $h = \tilde{h} = 15$ mm.

At the upper and lower boundaries of the layer, normal stresses are specified in the form of a unit wave with a negative sign, shifted from zero by an amount $-b$ along the z -axis, and an asymmetric positive unit wave (shifted from zero by an amount $+b$ along the z -axis):

$$\sigma_y^{(h)}(x, z) = \sigma_y^{(\tilde{h})}(x, z) - 10^8$$

$$= \frac{-10^8}{((z-b)^2 + 10^2)^2 \cdot (x^2 + 10^2)^2} + \frac{10^8}{((z+b)^2 + 10^2)^2 \cdot (x^2 + 10^2)^2}$$

and zero tangential stresses

$$\tau_{yx}^{(h)} = \tau_{yz}^{(h)} = \tau_{yx}^{(\tilde{h})} = \tau_{yz}^{(\tilde{h})} = 0.$$

The infinite system was truncated at $m=5$ (order of the system of equations).

The accuracy of the boundary conditions at the specified m and given geometric parameters is at least 10^{-8} for values from 0 to 1.

For verification, the obtained stress state results were compared with the work [15].

Conclusions. This paper presents a method for solving a spatial elasticity problem for a semi-infinite layer bounded by two horizontal and one vertical surfaces. This method is important for analyzing engineering structures in the aerospace industry and mechanical engineering, where elements often have complex geometries and are subjected to stresses that can lead to failure.

The main results and achievements obtained in the course of the research are as follows:

1. A new approach for analyzing a semi-infinite layer has been developed. The proposed method is based on a combination of the generalized Fourier method and the principle of load asymmetry. This made it possible to take into account the influence of the vertical free boundary, which is a significant advantage over classical approaches, which usually cannot take into account the side boundaries.

2. The mathematical apparatus has been simplified. The application of the asymmetry principle has made it possible to reduce the complex boundary value problem for a semi-infinite layer to the already studied problem for an infinite layer, which has greatly simplified the solution process.

3. High accuracy of calculations is ensured. The numerical implementation of the solution of the system of equations was performed using the reduction method. This made it possible to achieve a high, predetermined accuracy of at least

10⁻⁸ when performing boundary conditions.

4. The results were validated. The obtained results were compared with known solutions and checked for compliance with boundary conditions. This confirms the reliability and effectiveness of the proposed method.

In general, the proposed method is a powerful analytical tool for high-precision calculation of the stress-

strain state of semi-infinite layers. This approach can be used for further research, in particular for the analysis of dynamic loads and interactions with various types of inclusions and damage.

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